

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

The Basic Concept of Cyber Crime

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Abstract

Cyber Crime is a common phenomenon in the world. Cyber Crime is that group of activities made by the people by creating disturbance in network, stealing others important and private data, documents, hack bank details and accounts and transferring money to their own. Cyber Crime, especially through the Internet, has grown in importance as the computer has become central to commerce, entertainment, and government. Cybercrime, also called computer crime, the use of a computer as an instrument to further illegal ends, such as committing fraud, Trafficking in child pornography and intellectual property, stealing identities, or violating privacy. The cybercrime and they its impacts over the society in the form of economical disrupt, psychological disorder, threat to National defense etc. Restriction of cyber-crimes is dependent on proper analysis of their behavior and understanding of their impacts over various levels of society. Now a day's Cybercrime is increasing day by day. People have been greatly suffering for it. It is not only creates human suffering but also put effect on it. So Cyber Crime is one of the major crimes done by computer expert. This paper gives the basic concept of cybercrime.

Keywords: Cyber Crime; Criminal; Child Pornography; Computer Crime; Human Suffering

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1. Introduction

Cyber Crime is not an old sort of crime to the world. It is defined as any criminal activity which takes place on or over the medium of computers or internet or other technology recognized by the Information Technology Act. There are number of illegal activities which are committed over the internet by technically skilled criminals. Taking a wider interpretation, it can be said that, Cyber Crime includes any illegal activity where computer or internet is either a tool or target or both. Cyber Crime is an uncontrollable evil having its base in the misuse of growing dependence on computers in modern life. Usage of computer and other allied technology in daily life is growing rapidly and has become an urge which facilitates user convenience. It is a medium which is infinite and immeasurable. Some of the newly emerged cybercrimes are cyber-stalking, cyber-terrorism, e-mail spoofing, e-mail bombing, cyber pornography, cyber-defamation etc. Some conventional crimes may also come under the category of cybercrimes if they are committed through the medium of computer or Internet (Chaubey, 2012).

Cybercrime is a term used to broadly describe criminal activity in which computers or computer networks are a tool, a target, or a place of criminal activity and include everything from electronic cracking to denial-of-service attacks. It is also used to include traditional crimes in which computers or networks are used to enable the illicit activity. The Cyber Crime can halt any railway where it is, it may misguide the planes on its flight by misguiding with wrong signals, it may cause any important military data to fall in the hands of foreign countries, and it may halt e-media and every system can collapse within a fraction of seconds (Nayak, October 2013). Cybercrime is growing and current technical models to tackle cybercrime are inefficient in stemming the increase in cybercrime. This serves to indicate that further preventive strategies are required in order to reduce cybercrime. Just as it is important to understand the characteristics of the criminals in order to understand the motivations behind the crime and subsequently develop and deploy crime prevention strategies, it is also important to understand victims, i.e., the characteristics of the users of computer systems in order to understand the way these users fall